

Substituent Effect on the Absorption Spectra of Mesoionic 1, 3, 4-Thiadiazoles

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Mesoionic compounds like sydrones (I), and 1, 3, 4-thiadiazoles (II) are also classified as *pseudo-aromatic* compounds^{1,2}. On this basis, the long-wave length band around 400 m μ , characteristic² of the mesoionic ring (II), as well as the C-S frequency were recently shown³ to obey a fairly good linear relationship⁴ against σ values for R in III ($Y = [\text{CH}_2]_0$) indicating the presence of delocalised sextet in the heterocyclic ring.

We now wish to point out that further refinement of data is possible through Yukawa-Tsuno equation⁵ when the previously derived regression line, $10^4/\lambda \text{ max} = 25.93 (\pm 0.0015) - 1.253 \sigma$; $r = 0.975$, for a series of *para*-(NO₂, CN, I, Br, Cl, Me and MeO-) and *meta*-(NO₂, I, Br, Cl, EtO) substituents, tends to improve the fit by using $\sigma_{\text{eff}} = \sigma + 1.37 (\bar{\sigma} - \sigma)$ giving $\rho = -1.13$, $r = 0.982$, $s = 0.0705$. But the improvement was only marginal ($\rho = -1.06$, $r = 0.983$, $s = 0.0108$) with $\sigma_{\text{eff}} = \sigma + 1.67 (\bar{\sigma} - \sigma)$. These calculations are based on the assumption⁶ that $\bar{\sigma} = \sigma$ or σ^o for all the *para*-substituents other than NO₂ and CN groups. At any event, a large positive value of R in Yukawa-Tsuno equation strongly suggests additional resonance effects of *para*-substituents in phenyl ring at C₅ in III ($Y = [\text{CH}_2]_0$).

In support of these conclusions some additional experimental results are summarised below. Thus condensation⁷ of potassium phenyl di-thiocarbazonate with acyl chlorides of phenyl acetic acid, β -phenyl propionic acid and cinnamic acid furnished the respective mesoionic compounds (III) in 15–20% yield and the relevant data are shown in Table 1 with those of known 4,5-diphenyl derivative^{3,7}.

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The data contained in Table 1 clearly demonstrate the existence of inter-nucleus conjugation through C₅ and this is more or less completely inhibited by the insulating effect of a single methylene group so much so that $\lambda_{\max}$ for III ($Y = [\text{CH}_2]_{1 \text{ or } 2}$) is comparable to those reported^{2,7} for 3-phenyl-5-alkyl derivatives (II, R = Ph, R₁ = Alkyl). Moreover, conjugation is apparently revived through an ethylenic bridge at C₅; and the observed red-shift coupled with relatively high $\epsilon_{\max}$ as well as IR data are possible indications of *trans*-orientation around the ethylenic bond.

TABLE 1

*Properties of Mesoionic Compounds (III)**

Y =	m.p. °C	$\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) m μ (ϵ)	Major IR bands in chf. (ν , cm ⁻¹)	
			c-s	others
(CH ₂) ₀	228	397(5240)	1332	
(CH ₂) ₁	205d	365(3250)	1328	1600(w), 915(w)
(CH ₂) ₂	188-89	362(3650)	1322	1595(w), 915(w)
-CH=CH-	230-31	445(10900)	1332, 1305 (Split)	1616(m, -C=C-, Str), 1595(w, Sh) 952(m, -C-H, O.P) 915(w)

*Satisfactory analyses have been obtained.

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